

Report on First Symposium of European Researchers in Japan

By Wilfried Wunderlich and Eckhard Hitzer

On Saturday, 21st of October 2023, in the Europa House in Tokyo, the first Symposium of European Researchers in Japan took place under the title: “Past, Present and Future Cross-continental Connections between Europe and Japan”, jointly organized by four national organizations of foreign researchers in Japan (the Spanish Asociacion de Cientificos Espanoles en Japon (ACE) [1], the Association of Italian Researchers in Japan (AIRJ) [2], the German JSPS Alumni Association [3] and the French Sciencescope Association [4]) and by the Delegation of the European Union in Japan.

In his opening remarks, the new Head of Science, Innovation, Digital, and Other EU Policies Section, Delegation of the European Union to Japan, Mr. Gijs Berends, explained the discrepancy between scientific findings and their translation into practical policy guidelines.

Fig. 1. From left to right, speakers of the first technical session in the morning: Michele Guarnieri (AIRJ), Cécile Asanuma-Brice (Sciencescope), Jose M. M. Caaveiro (ACE), Eckhard Hitzer (JSPS Club). Photo: Olaf Karthaus.

In the first technical session in the morning with the topic: “Dependence of Societies on Scientific Research”, four lectures were given. First, by the Spanish ACE member and vaccine developer Jose M. M. Caaveiro, Kyushu University, who envisions the challenge of developing future vaccines in only one hundred days. For him vaccines have saved millions of lives and come with a minor negligible risk of side effects of the order one in a million. In the

following Q&A session (see Fig. 1) this view was challenged referring to the strong negative side effects the HPV virus vaccine has had 2013 in Japan [5].

Second, the JSPS Club member, physicist Eckhard Hitzer of International Christian University and Visiting Fellow for *religious, philosophical and scientific foundations of sustainable society* at the European Institute, Sophia University, addressed “Scientific Research - Opportunities and Pitfalls” in his talk. Opportunities on the one hand to sustain life, diagnose and cure disease, serious pitfalls on the other hand are the destruction of life, creation of disease and total surveillance.

The third morning presentation, by Dr. Cécile Asanuma-Brice (representing the French Sciencescope), co-director of the Mitate Laboratory in Fukushima, focused on learning lessons from the Fukushima accident and developing organizational guidelines should another nuclear disaster occur.

In the final presentation in this session, Michele Guarnieri of the Hibot robotics company reported on robot deployments in technical facilities such as aircraft tanks or boilers in chemical factories to inspect damaged areas.

Apart from morning and afternoon coffee breaks, a light sandwich lunch was served, all offering ample opportunity to catch up with old friends and engage in networking.

In the afternoon Dalibor P. Drljaca, EU Representative of Horizon Europe, gave a detailed introduction to Horizon Europe and the application and evaluation procedure. Then Prof. em. Dr. Tetsuya Mizutomo, Executive Director of JSPS shared his insights on Open Science and its effect on Society. This was continued by former Japan Times journalist Ms. Magdalena Osumi, now at BCW Global, reflecting on science communication in Europe and Japan.

Fig. 2. From left to right, the representatives of the four associations: Heinrich Menkhaus (JSPS Club), Cecile Laly (Sciencescope), Sarah Cosentino (AIRJ), Daniel del Barrio Alvarez (ACE). Photo: Olaf Karthaus.

The event continued in the afternoon with greetings from representatives of the four organizations (see Fig. 2): Dr. Daniel del Barrio Alvarez (The University of Tokyo) for the Spanish “ACE Japon”, Dr. Sarah Cosentino (The University of Tokyo) for the Italian “AIRJ”, Dr. Heinrich Menkhaus (Meiji University) for the German JSPS Alumni Association and Dr. Cecile Laly (Kyoto Seika University) for the French “Sciencescope”. The JSPS Club is one of the oldest organizations of foreign scientists in Japan with a wide member base both in Germany and Japan and with regular conferences communicating science to the public, a special prize supported by ANA, and also a special category for institutional members. All organizations receive some organizational support from their embassies and culture centers in Japan, but in the end it is voluntary work on top of their daily duties in research and teaching. There is the hope to possibly found in the future a European Researcher Association in Japan,

also including nationals from other smaller European countries. In attendance were also individual researchers from Greece, Norway and Denmark. The need of support for individual foreign students and academics in Japan in case of academic harassment, problems and conflicts with hosts and employers was also pointed out. Furthermore, the Italian AIRJ provides exemplary support for members to plan their future pension, which in the case of international mobility spanning countries with diverse pension systems and with huge currency value fluctuations is quite a complex question.

The meeting concluded with free style conversations over a glass of wine, provided by the four associations that cooperated on the event. It was the first joint event of the four national alumni associations hosted by the Delegation of the European Union in Japan. About forty listeners, mainly young scholarship holders, were present.

[1] ASSOCIATION OF SPANISH RESEARCHERS IN JAPAN (ACE), <https://en.acejapon.jp/>, access 23 Oct. 2023.

[2] Association of Italian Researchers in Japan (AIRJ), <https://www.airj.info/>, access 23 Oct. 2023.

[3] German JSPS Alumni Association, <https://www.jsp-club.de/en/about-us/the-jsp-club>, access 23 Oct. 2023.

[4] The Association for French-speaking students and researchers in Japan Sciencescope, <https://www.sciencescope.org/>, access 23 Oct. 2023.

[5] “According to a report in the Japan Times, 8.29 million people had received the HPV vaccine as of December 2012, and there were 1968 cases of concerning adverse events reported as of March 2013. Of these adverse events, 106 were described as "serious cases of pains or body convulsions, pains in joints, or difficulty in walking." Those numbers translate to a rate of 12.8 serious cases of adverse events per 1 million inoculations ... “ (Nick Mulcahy, Japan Withdraws HPV Vaccine Recommendation for Girls, in Medscape Medical News, <https://www.medscape.com/viewarticle/806645?form=fpf>, access 22 Oct. 2023).